

Spotlight

Novel antagonists reveal the mechanism of PXR inhibition

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The pregnane X receptor (PXR) is a key regulator of metabolism, but the mechanisms underlying its antagonism remain unclear. Garcia-Maldonado *et al.* reported potent new antagonists and their co-crystal structures, revealing molecular determinants of PXR antagonism and paving the way for developing antagonists as therapeutics and preventing undesirable PXR activation.

The PXR (NR1I2) (see Glossary) plays a crucial role in the transcriptional regulation of genes involved in drug metabolism and disposition. As a ligand-activated nuclear receptor (NR), PXR is often referred to as a xenobiotic receptor due to its activation by various xenobiotics and drugs. The flexibility and promiscuity of PXR's ligand-binding domain (LBD) enable it to interact with a wide range of structurally diverse ligands of varying sizes and shapes, making this characteristic a unique feature of PXR [1,2].

Upon activation, PXR functions as a transcription factor, leading primarily to upregulation (induction) of its target genes. Among these, CYP3A4 (cytochrome P450 3A4) is the primary target gene and the most important drug-metabolizing enzyme (Figure 1A). Other essential enzymes and transporters involved in phase I and II of xenobiotic metabolism and elimination, including CYP2C9, CYP2B6, CYP2C19, CYP3A5, and CYP2A6, conjugation enzymes such as UGT1A1, UGT1A3, UGT1A4, SULT2A1, and the transporter

P-glycoprotein/MDR1, are also upregulated through PXR activation [3]. Due to the ability of activated PXR to upregulate multiple drug-metabolizing enzymes and augment drug clearance, drug–drug interactions (DDIs) pose a significant risk, especially when multiple drugs are co-administered [1]. In addition, PXR activation adversely affects various metabolic functions, including lipid and cholesterol metabolism, glucose tolerance, and blood pressure. Thus, it has been hypothesized that PXR activation may partly explain the adverse metabolic effects associated with exposure to environmental chemicals and certain drugs [4].

A better understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying activation by agonists and deactivation by antagonists holds promise for identifying therapeutic avenues aimed at conditions involving PXR activation and for developing safer drugs to mitigate DDIs [5,6]. PXR shares structural characteristics with other NRs [2]. The LBD of PXR is characterized by an α -helical sandwich structure complemented by five-stranded antiparallel β -sheets. Notably, the ligand-binding pocket (LBP) of PXR is large (1300–1544 Å³), displaying dynamic and flexible properties that allow it to accommodate and bind bulky or multiple ligands simultaneously. Historically, most crystal structures of the PXR LBD with agonists have primarily depicted the receptor in its active state, facilitating interactions with coactivators through its activation function-2 (AF-2) region [7].

The LBP of the PXR receptor, which makes it evolutionarily tuned to activate the receptor, coupled with its remarkable promiscuity, has posed significant challenges in developing potent and selective PXR antagonists [5,6]. Only a limited number of potent inverse agonists or antagonists have been identified, with SPA70 being one of the few molecules currently known to effectively modulate PXR activity [8]. Notably, a crystal structure of PXR

Glossary

Activation function-2 (AF-2): a structural domain found in nuclear receptors that is crucial for their transcriptional activity. AF-2 is located in the PXR LBD (α 3/4/5/12) and is responsible for recruiting coregulators upon ligand binding.

Agonist/antagonist: an agonist is a ligand that binds to a receptor and activates it, mimicking the effect of an endogenous ligand. In contrast, an antagonist is a molecule that binds to a receptor without intrinsic activity, thereby blocking or reducing the action of an agonist or endogenous ligand.

Coactivators: proteins or complexes that enhance gene expression by associating with agonist-bound NR.

CYP3A4: cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4) is an important enzyme predominantly located in the liver and intestines. It plays a major role in the oxidative metabolism of xenobiotics, including various toxins and drugs, facilitating their biotransformation and subsequent elimination from the body.

Drug–drug interactions (DDI): occur when the effects of a drug are altered by the activity of another drug. These interactions can enhance or reduce the efficacy of one or both drugs and may increase the risk of adverse effects.

Induction: transcriptional upregulation of a xenobiotic-metabolizing enzyme through the activation of nuclear receptors or aryl hydrocarbon receptor by a ligand.

Nuclear receptor (NR): a class of proteins located within cells that mediate the activities of steroid and thyroid hormones, as well as certain other molecules. When bound by their ligands, NRs act as transcription factors, regulating the expression of target genes.

Pregnane X receptor (PXR): PXR is an NR that mainly regulates the expression of genes involved in drug metabolism. It is activated by a variety of endogenous and exogenous substances, including xenobiotics and steroids.

SRC-1 (steroid receptor coactivator-1): a transcriptional coactivator that interacts with NRs to enhance gene expression.

Xenobiotics: any substance that is foreign to living systems, including drugs, environmental contaminants (e.g., pesticides), and industrial compounds.

bound to an antagonist has been absent, leaving the molecular mechanism of PXR antagonism unknown.

In a recent study, Garcia-Maldonado *et al.*, from Taosheng Chen's laboratory, revealed a novel PXR antagonist, SJPYT-310, bound to the PXR LBD and described the co-crystal structure at a resolution of 2.35 Å [7]. Through the co-crystal analysis, they detailed specific interactions of the

Figure 1. Structural Insights into antagonist-bound pregnane X receptor (PXR) and molecular mechanism of PXR antagonism. (A) PXR-mediated transcriptional regulation of drug-metabolizing enzymes. Upon ligand activation with a drug or xenobiotic, PXR forms heterodimers with other nuclear receptors (NRs), such as retinoid X receptor α (RXR α). This complex binds to the PXR response elements (PXRRE) in the promoter regions of target genes. Subsequently, the receptors recruit transcriptional coactivators [e.g., steroid receptor coactivator-1 (SRC-1)], leading to the augmented transcription of target genes (e.g., CYP3A4, CYP2C9, UGT1A1, and ABCB1). (B) List of amino acids of the PXR ligand-binding domain (LBD) suggested by Garcia-Maldonado *et al.* [8] to interact with antagonist molecules. The leucine cage and π -trap enhance binding affinity and potency. Residues of the α 12 helix that should not interact with a PXR antagonist to avoid stabilization of the activation function-2 (AF-2) domain. (C) Surface crystal structures of PXR LBD (light pink) with coactivator SRC-1 (green) and embedded modulators located at the center of the PXR cavity [right; Protein Data Bank (PDB) ID: 5X0R]. Agonist (sky-blue) and antagonist (olive) cartoon structures are shown. The broken circle indicates the ‘hydrophobic α 12 cleft’ with agonist interaction. Coactivator SRC-1 residues are highlighted and the L428-L690 residues are shown for their key interactions in agonist activation (right; PDB ID: 8SV0). Figures were created with PyMol and ChimeraX, and compiled with BioRender (www.biorender.com).

antagonist SJPYT-310 with the hydrophobic ‘ π -trap’ consisting of the F288, W299, and Y306 residues, as well as a ‘leucine cage’ composed of the L206, L209, L239, and L240 residues of the PXR LBD (Figure 1B) [7,9]. More importantly, the co-crystal structure mapping the interactions of SJPYT-310 with individual residues of the PXR cavity allowed them to focus in detail on mechanistic aspects of PXR antagonism and the interactions of both PXR agonists and antagonists with residues of helix 12 (α 12) in the AF-2 surface domain, which is critical for the activation or inhibition. Garcia-Maldonado *et al.*

found that the antagonist binding induces specific structural rearrangements in the α 12 region – a phenomenon not observed in PXR agonist structures [7]. The antagonist SJPYT-310 destabilizes the active α 12 conformation, preventing coactivator binding. Specifically, it reorients the phenyl ring of F251 and shifts residues L428 and F429 within the α 12 helix, leaving the hydrophobic cleft formed by residues M425, L428, and F429 in the α 12 helix unoccupied. SJPYT-310 also positions L428 in the PXR too far from L690, a key residue in the LXXLL NR binding motif of the **steroid receptor coactivator-1 (SRC-1)**,

with a distance of 5.02 Å (Figure 1C) [7]. In contrast, SJB7, a structurally similar PXR agonist, was shown to occupy the hydrophobic cleft and stabilize the α 12 helix to enable coactivator binding (Figure 1C) [7].

Based on the uncovered structural determinants of PXR antagonism, Garcia-Maldonado *et al.* designed and synthesized the compound SJPYT-331, which is currently the most potent PXR antagonist with an IC_{50} of 7.1 ± 0.8 nM. SJPYT-331 exhibits strong antagonistic effects in cellular assays and in regulating CYP3A4 mRNA in primary human hepatocytes [7].

In the subsequent experiments using molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, which allow for large-scale analysis of α 12 helix movement, Garcia-Maldonado *et al.* confirmed that the novel antagonists reposition the α 12 helix into the outward position, preventing the binding of the coactivator SRC-1 peptide. In contrast, the PXR agonists used in this study were found to stabilize the α 12 helix in the inward position [7]. Overall, these findings indicate that the α 12 AF-2 region serves as a crucial gatekeeper, determining whether a drug acts as a PXR activator or inhibitor based on its conformation [7].

Nevertheless, additional validation of these findings is still required. Future research should use larger-scale MD simulations or biophysical experimental analyses to better corroborate the proposed mechanism. Furthermore, the crystallization of antagonist-bound PXR LBD in complex with a corepressor is essential to confirm the mechanism of PXR antagonism. Further evaluation is also necessary to determine the effectiveness of novel antagonists and to describe their PXR inverse agonistic activity. This assessment should include comprehensive *in vitro* studies involving multiple cellular experiments with various PXR agonists. Additionally, exploring the therapeutic potential *in vivo* warrants investigation using humanized PXR mouse models.

The elucidation of the structural mechanism of PXR antagonism by Garcia-Maldonado *et al.* paves the way for developing even more effective and selective PXR antagonists with potent effects on the regulation of metabolic genes *in vivo*. The discovery of potent PXR antagonists may facilitate studies on their therapeutic utility in preventing DDIs and mitigating chemoresistance [10], as well as in the treatment of conditions such as hemorrhagic shock- and drug-induced liver injuries, hyperglycemia, hypercholesterolemia, inflammation, and hepatic steatosis mediated by PXR activation [4].

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests. P.P. is an advisor in Lipidera Therapeutics company.

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References

1. Sinz, M.W. (2013) Evaluation of pregnane X receptor (PXR)-mediated CYP3A4 drug-drug interactions in drug development. *Drug Metab. Rev.* 45, 3–14

2. Kamaraj, R. *et al.* (2022) Allosteric antagonism of the pregnane X receptor (PXR): current-state-of-the-art and prediction of novel allosteric sites. *Cells* 11, 2974
3. Pavek, P. (2016) Pregnane X receptor (PXR)-mediated gene repression and cross-talk of PXR with other nuclear receptors via coactivator interactions. *Front. Pharmacol.* 7, 456
4. Karpale, M. *et al.* (2022) Nuclear receptor PXR in drug-induced hypercholesterolemia. *Cells* 11, 313
5. Lin, W. *et al.* (2023) Structure-guided approach to modulate small molecule binding to a promiscuous ligand-activated protein. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 120, e2217804120
6. Huber, A.D. *et al.* (2023) Ligand flexibility and binding pocket malleability cooperate to allow selective PXR activation by analogs of a promiscuous nuclear receptor ligand. *Structure* 31, 1545–1555.e49
7. Garcia-Maldonado, E. *et al.* (2024) Chemical manipulation of an activation/inhibition switch in the nuclear receptor PXR. *Nat. Commun.* 15, 4054
8. Lin, W. *et al.* (2017) SPA70 is a potent antagonist of human pregnane X receptor. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 741
9. Rashidian, A. *et al.* (2022) Discrepancy in interactions and conformational dynamics of pregnane X receptor (PXR) bound to an agonist and a novel competitive antagonist. *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.* 20, 3004–3018
10. Niu, X. *et al.* (2022) Insights into the critical role of the PXR in preventing carcinogenesis and chemotherapeutic drug resistance. *Int. J. Biol. Sci.* 18, 742–759